

THE
SCYTODIDAE
OF
SOUTH AFRICA

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THE SCYTODIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The family Scytodidae is a small family represented by 5 genus and 245 species and has a worldwide distribution. From South Africa a single genus *Scytodes* represented by 30 species are known. Twenty-three of the species are South African endemics but 16 of these species are known only from one sex and seven are known only from the type locality this resulted in 37% of the species being listed as Data Deficient. Two species are introduced *Scytodes fusca* Walckenaer, 1837 and *Scytodes thoracica* (Latreille, 1802) and two are African endemics and two southern African endemics. A large percentage (57%) are listed as Least Concern and only two species are presently of special concern. *Scytodes gooldi* Purcell, 1904 known from a small area in the Western Cape is experiencing ongoing loss of habitat to crop cultivation and housing development therefore listed as Vulnerable under criterion B. *Scytodes montana* Purcell, 1904 only known from one sex has a restricted distribution and is listed as Rare. The African species of the genus has not yet been revised and more species are expected.

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Scytodes sp.

* Not listed for South Africa in World Spider Catalog (2021)

FAMILY SCYTODIDAE Blackwall, 1864

The family Scytodidae is a small family represented by 5 genus and 245 species and has a wide distribution (World Spider Catalog 2020). From South Africa a single genus *Scytodes* represented by 30 species of which 22 are South African endemics.

COMMON NAME: Spitting spiders

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 4-9 mm. Colour: body pale yellow to brown with carapace and abdomen having dark stripes or spots joined to form symmetrical patterns. Carapace domed towards thoracic region to accommodate the large glue-producing glands; eyes: 6 small eyes, arranged in 3 well separated groups, each pair contiguous; sternum oval, with sclerotized edge; apex blunt. Abdomen broad, oval with a light covering of dark setae; venter with chitinous depressions behind genital groove; colulus large, pointed, with numerous setae; anterior spinnerets contiguous, slightly larger than other spinnerets. Legs long and slender with light covering of short dark setae, strong setae absent; tarsi with three claws with onychium; metatarsi longer than tarsi.

LIFESTYLE: Scytodids are nocturnal cursorial spiders and have a specialized way of catching prey. They are the only spiders known to possess special glands in their carapace that produce silky glue. The enormous glands consist of 2 parts: the anterior part produces venom and the posterior part synthesizes gluey silk. The gluey silk is a fibrous glycoprotein. Rapid contraction of the carapace muscles squirts a mixture of venom and gluey silk from the chelicerae over a distance of 1.5-2 cm. The prey is stuck to the substrate and becomes paralyzed. The eggs are simply held together by a few silk threads and carried in the chelicerae. The species found in houses move slowly, and usually roam around in closets and dark cupboards stalking prey like fish moths and other small soft-bodied invertebrates. Due to their colour and markings on the carapace, they are frequently confused for the violin spider. They are found in all the biomes throughout the region. They are commonly collected from vegetation (tree and herb layer) and from under stones and dark places on the soil surface.

TAXONOMY: African genera not revised

Scytodes sp. Photo Len de Beer

Scytodes sp. Photo Peter Webb

GENUS SCYTODES Latreille, 1804

COMMON NAME: Spitting Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Scytodes thoracica* (Latreille, 1802)

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: both sexes small to medium-sized, rarely more than 10 mm. Colour of body pale yellow to dark brown, carapace and abdomen with dark stripes or spots that form species-specific symmetrical patterns. Carapace domed towards thoracic region to accommodate the large, glue-producing glands; eyes: six small eyes arranged in three well-separated groups, each pair contiguous. Abdomen broad, oval, with a sparse covering of dark setae. Legs long and slender with light covering of short dark setae, strong setae absent.

LIFESTYLE: *Scytodes* are free-running, nocturnal spiders that are usually found in dark places, e.g. under stones and logs, leaf litter, under tree bark, in caves or in buildings. Spitting spiders are unique in that they squirt a mixture of silky glue and venom from their chelicerae to catch prey and as a defense mechanism against predators. They prey on any small invertebrates, but especially on termites and silverfish. Some species aggregate in small groups of up to 30 individuals under logs and rocks, which include adult and immature spiders. An untidy network of silk threads is spun across the substrate, but it is not clear whether the spiders use this as a capture web. The female builds a silk retreat with a few threads during egg-laying. Scytodids lack tubuliform glands and the eggs are simply held together by a few silk threads and carried in the chelicerae. Scytodids occur in a wide variety of habitats throughout the Afrotropical Region. They are often collected from vegetation (tree and herb layer) and in pitfall traps. Van der Merwe (1994) collected 175 specimens, representing five species, in montane forest in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. Two cosmopolitan species, *S. fusca* Walckenaer and *S. thoracica* Latreille, are commonly encountered in houses where they have been observed to prey on silver-fish.

TAXONOMY: African species not yet revised

Scytodidae. a: *Scytodes* sp., female, dorsal view; b: body, ventral view; c: eye pattern, dorsal view; d: epigyne; e: male palp, lateral view; f: carapace, lateral view (after Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997)

Scytodes arenacea Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Arid Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African species described by Purcell (1904) from Beenbreek in Kenhardt district, in the Northern Cape. Recorded also from Namibia. In South Africa known only from the Northern Cape (EOO=75 019 km²; AOO=28 km²; 635-1172 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: Kenhardt (-29.34, 21.15); Orange River (-29.66, 24.2); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44); Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42); Beenbreek (-29.24, 18.33); (-28.82, 24.82); Swartduinkop (-28.53, 19.25); Gams (-29.14,18.57); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering ground dwellers collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. This species is common in the arid regions of the Northern Cape and sampled from the Desert, Succulent and Nama Karoo and Savanna biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018), Augrabies National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2021) and Benfontein Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from female, not illustrated. Carapace with three stripes that pass the eyes to the front; femora yellow only few dots forming feeble distal band; abdomen with small black spots; in female horny plates ventrally on abdomen, shaped) (wide apart. (Purcell 1904)

Scytodes arenacea female from Tswalu GR Photo Peter Webb

Scytodes arenacea female Photos ASD

Scytodes broomi Pocock, 1902

COMMON NAME: Northern Cape Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape species described by Pocock (1902) from Garies. Recorded from several localities in the Northern Cape (EOO=34 764 km²; AOO=12 km²; 231-1172 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape*: Garies (-30.56, 17.97); Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.82, 24.82).

LIFESTYLE: Free living ground spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. Sampled from the Grassland and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. It is protected in the Benfontein Nature Reserve but some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from only the female, epigyne illustrated. Carapace ornamented with yellow and black bands of about equal width; an anterior black patch covers the median eyes; a black stripe extends backwards on each side of the middle line, over the lateral eyes, and stops short just past the middle of the carapace in front of the highest point of the eminence. Legs yellow and black; coxae black in front, trochanter with an anterior black spot; femora largely blackish in front. Abdomen ornamented above with four rows of black spots; blackish beneath (Pocock 1902) .

After Pocock (1902)

Scytodes caffra Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Dark Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described by Purcell (1904) from Zululand. The species is known from three African countries. In South Africa it is recorded from five provinces (EOO=615 772 km²; AOO= 156 km²; 1-1690 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, it is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, Swaziland, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene Smuts House (-25.89, 28.23); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/ Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Klipriviersberg NR Site 1 (-26.3112, 28.0026); Klipriviersberg NR Site 2A (-26.3075, 28.0147); Klipriviersberg NR Site 4 (-26.2908, 28.0789); Klipriviersberg NR Site 5 (-26.2912, 28.0277); Bronkhorstspuit (-25.80, 28.74); Bronkhorstspuit to Groblersdal (-25.6183, 29.0317). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Ndumo Game Reserve S E boulder (-26.87, 32.24); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Umfolozi Nature Reserve (-28.3, 31.76); Van Reenen (-28.37, 29.38); Umfolosi Drift (-28.33, 31.08); Midlands Mount Shannon Farm (-29.6508, 29.9761); Ingwavuma (-27.12, 32.01);); Legalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Lwakahle) (-25.43, 31.75); Kruger National Park (Makhuthwanini) 04 (-25.38, 31.6); Kruger National Park (Napi) (-25.37, 31.51); Kruger National Park (Randspruit) (-25.28, 31.64); Kruger National Park (Satara) (-24.38, 31.78); Kruger National Park (Sabiepoort 11 (-25.19, 32.2); Kruger National Park (Vutome) (-25.24, 32.08) **Western Cape:** Hermanus, Hoy's Kopje, Overberg (-34.4, 19.25); Fernkloof Nature Reserve (-34.86, 19.34); Sedgefield (-34.03, 22.81).

LIFESTYLE: Free-living ground dweller. The species was sampled from the Fynbos, Forest, Grassland, and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013) as well as from commercial pine plantations (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

Scytodes caffra female Photo Les Oates

After Lawrence (1937)

After Purcell(1904)

Scytodes caffra female and male Photo ASD

Scytodes caffra (continued)

CONSERVATION MEASURES : There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the following protected areas: Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006), Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015), Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020), Legalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016), Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) and Fernkloof Nature Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from both sexes. Carapace black, the anterior two-thirds with a median yellow stripe containing a narrow, median black line which almost reaches to middle of carapace ; posterior surface of carapace with median yellow patch; sides with 4 tiers of rather small yellow spots; carapace very high, its posterior surface almost vertical, its superior-anterior surface sloping at an angle of about 45° to the horizontal. Sternum black. Abdomen transversely striped with black and yellow. Legs with femora infusate (Purcell 1904).

Scytodes caffra female epigyne, sternum and carapace from Vermont Photo Victor Hamilton-Atwell

Scytodes caffra female from Pretoria Photo Les Oates

Scytodes caffra female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Scytodes cedri Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Cederberg Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African species described by Purcell (1904) from the Keurbosch Kraal River Cederberg range, Clanwilliam. Recorded from two provinces (EOO=125 446 km²; AOO=72 km²; 15-1513 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and can therefore be listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Jeffreysbay (-34.04, 24.94). **Western Cape:** Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89); De Hoop Nature Reserve, De Hoop Vlei, S shore (-34.36, 20.38); De Hoop Nature Reserve Potberg (-34.45, 20.44); De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44); Marloth Nature Reserve, Swellendam District (-34.25, 20.57); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Hermanus (-34.40, 19.25); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal (522 m a.s.l. (-32.2795, 19.2192); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal (531 m a.s.l. (-32.2802, 19.2198); Cederberg Wilderness Area Wupperthal (515 m a.s.l. (-32.2793, 19.220); Cederberg Wilderness Area Niewoudt's Pass 527 m a.s.l.(-32.3495, 19.0071); Cederberg Wilderness Area Niewoudt's Pass (-32.3503, 19.0073); Cederberg Niewoudt's Pass 551 m a.s.l (-32.3489, 19.0062); Cederberg Niewoudts Pass 565 m a.s.l. (-32.3482, 19.0048); Cederberg Wilderness Area 643 m a.s.l. (-32.3958, 19.08730); Cederberg Wilderness Area 677 m a.s.l. (-32.3968, 19.0870); Cederberg Wilderness Area 152 m a.s.l. (-32.4607, 19.2395); Cederberg Wilderness Area 1337 m a.s.l. (-32.4347, 19.2157); Cederberg Aan Het Berg 251 m a.s.l. (-32.2774, 18.5308); Cederberg Sawadee 359 m a.s.l. (-32.3386, 18.9901); Cederberg Sawadee (-32.3373, 18.9911); Cederberg Sawadee 344 m a.s.l. (-32.3378, 18.9884); Cederberg Sawadee 332 m a.s.l.(-32.3388, 18.9878); Cederberg Crystal Pools Wupperthal (-32.3110, 19.1706); Cederberg Crystal Pools Wupperthal (-32.3099, 19.1754).

LIFESTYLE: They are wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. Sampled from the Fynbos and Nama Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. The species protected in several protected areas such as Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020), Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006), De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009), Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2021), Cederberg Wilderness Area (Foord & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2016).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known only from the female, epigyne illustrated. Carapace with well developed mid black stripe reaching highest point lying between two yellow stripes from eyes to posterior edge where they merge; on both sides yellow stripe broad dark stripe. Abdomen pale yellow hardly spotted. Legs infusate.

After Purcell (1904)

Scytodes cedri undescribed male from Jeffreysbay Photo Linda Wiese

Scytodes clavata Benoit, 1965

COMMON NAME: Congo Spitting Spiders

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African species described by Benoit (1965) from the Democratic Republic of the Congo. Also recorded from South Africa from two provinces (EOO=75 878km²; AOO=20 km²; 804-2254 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Democratic Republic of the Congo, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Midlands Mount Shannon Farm (-29.4111, 29.584); Baynesfield Natal Midlands (29.7622, 30.3509). *Limpopo:* Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Vhembe Biosphere Thatevondo State Forest (22.9110, 30.3380).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in three protected areas: Blouberg Nature Reserve (Muelelwa et al. 2011), Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve and Thatevondo State Forest Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019)

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female. Carapace strongly domed, decorated with particular strong setae inserted on small promontories: these setae feel arched forward and their end is truncated (Benoit 1965)

After Benoit (1965)

Scytodes clavata undescribed male from Midlands Photo ASD

Scytodes constellata Lawrence, 1938

COMMON NAME: Nkandla Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African species described by Lawrence (1938) from Nkandla Forest. Although the type specimen was based on a juvenile the patterns on the body are distinct. Recorded from four provinces (EOO=161 281 km²; AOO=68 km²; 19-1512 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern but adults still need to be described.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cwebe Nature Reserve, The Haven (-32.28, 28.9); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37); Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64); Mkambati Nature Reserve (-31.31, 29.97). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Midlands Faberhill Farm (-29.6729, 29.9275). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm Balloon (-24.1994, 30.3388); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm Malta (-24.1617, 30.2538). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58); Kruger National Park (Vutome) (-25.24, 32.08); Kruger National Park (Skukuza) (-25, 31.97). Kruger National Park (Kambeni) (-25.153, 31.253); Kruger National Park (Shabeni) (-25.123, 31.237); Kruger National Park (Numbi) (-25.140, 31.208); Kruger National Park (Letaba Rest Camp) (-23.851, 31.577).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. Sampled from the Forest, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna (Foord et al. 2011) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Mkambati Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011), Kruger National Park (Robertson et al. 2011; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Legalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016)

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from a juvenile. Anterior surfaces of chelicerae with a blackish stripe along their inner margins. Abdomen above with a blackish median stripe in anterior half, the posterior half with wavy cross-bars, a horseshoe-shaped marking above the spinners (Lawrence 1938).

After Lawrence (1938)

Scytodes constellata from KZN Photo Andrea Sander

Scytodes drakensbergensis Lawrence, 1947

COMMON NAME: Drakensberg Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African species described by Lawrence (1947) from Van Reenen in KwaZulu-Natal. Recorded from two provinces (EOO=39 478km²; AOO=28 km²; 76-1703 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Clocolan, Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cathedral Peak (-28.94265, 29.18941); Royal Natal National Park (28.73, 28.923); Van Reenen (-28.37, 29.38); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79); Wakefield farm (-29.4733, 29.8925); Hluhluwe GR (-28.02, 32.28); Ithala Nature Reserve (-27.51, 31.23).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from vegetation or from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. Sampled from the Grassland biome (Haddad et al. 2013)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Mpetsane Conservation Estate, Vryheid Nature Reserve and Royal Natal National Park and Hluhluwe Game Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known only from female, illustrated. Carapace as in figure. Abdomen above and below speckled with larger and smaller dot-like markings arranged symmetrically. Legs: femora each with sub basal, median, and subapical hands, the middle one the widest; patellae blackish-brown in their apical halves; tibiae with narrow basal and apical blackish bands; metatarsi with an apical band and a second one near the base, both these bands less distinct than those of the other segments, especially in leg 1 (Lawrence 1947).

After Lawrence (1947)

Scytodes drakensbergensis from Ithala NR Photo Ernst Klimsa

Scytodes elizabethae Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Port Elizabeth Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African species described by Purcell (1904) from Port Elizabeth in the Eastern Cape. The species is recorded from four provinces (EOO=95 331km²; AOO=32 km²; 7-1816 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61). **Free State:** Wyndford Guest Farm Fouriesburg (-28.61, 28.23). **Gauteng:** Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve (-26.27, 28.08); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve Site 1 (-26.3112, 28.0026); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve Site 2A (-26.3075, 28.0147); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve Site 2B (-26.3075, 28.0147); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve Site 4 (-26.2908, 28.0789); Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve Site 7 (-26.2856, 28.0249); Sterkspruit Nature Reserve (-25.17, 30.54). **Mpumalanga:** Delmas (Farm Rietvallei) (-26.08, 28.57).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface in the Grassland (Haddad et al. 2013) and Thicket biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Klipriviersberg Nature Reserve and Sterkspruit Nature Reserve

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known only from male, palpal organ illustrated. Palpal organ with distal portion not straight but strongly sinuous (Purcell 1904). Carapace with three black stripes, median stripe reaching highest point; yellow lines that separate them thin; lateral stripes broad; side of carapace with series of tiers. Abdomen with transverse bands and spots. Leg femora infusate.

Scytodes elizabethae undescrbed female Photo Peter Webb

After Purcell (1904).

Scytodes elizabethae undescrbed female Photo Koos

Scytodes flagellata Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Long Palp Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African species described by Purcell (1904) from Houhoek, Caledon district in the Western Cape. Recorded from four provinces and protected in the Bontebok National Park (EOO=363 373 km²; AOO=32 km²; 63-1698 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Pretoria/Tshwane, Ingwe Bush Camp, Nootgedacht (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Midlands Mount Shannon Farm (-29.6508, 29.9761). **Mpumalanga:** Burgers Hall (-25.08, 31.06); Carolina (-26.06, 30.11). **Western Cape:** Caledon (-34.24, 19.43); Houhoek (-34.14, 19.04); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Kogelberg (-34.3262, 18.9712).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from vegetation tree and herb layer and from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known from both sexes, illustrated. Carapace with mesial yellow stripe dilated; with outer black stripes very broad with jagged outer and concave inner margins containing several small yellow dots; laterally with black reticulation; sternum spots. Abdomen with transverse black bands and speckled all over. Legs spotted and femora furnished with distal band; patella dark (Purcell 1904).

After Purcell (1904)

Scytodes flagellata male from Pretoria National Botanical Garden Photo ASD

Scytodes fusca Walckenaer, 1837

COMMON NAME: Dark Common Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A cosmopolitan species described by Walckenaer (1837). In South Africa recorded from six provinces (EOO=648 416 km²; AOO=52 km²; 16-1618 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide range it is therefore listed as of Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Central and southern America. Introduced to Europe and Africa etc.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91). **Gauteng:** Pretoria National Botanical Garden (-25.74, 28.19); Pretoria/Tshwane Ingwe Bush Camp, Nooitgedacht (-25.74, 28.19). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45). **Mpumalanga:** Komatipoort (-25.43, 31.94). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West, Farm 151b (-32.32, 22.45); Beaufort West, Farm Alexanderskraal (-32.58, 22.71); Fish Hoek, Peer Hill (residential) (-34.05, 18.35); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Robertson (-33.8, 19.87); Murraysburg farm Alexanderskraal (-32.23, 23.51).

LIFESTYLE: This is a species frequently found in houses. They are nocturnal cursorial spiders and have a specialized way of catching prey. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Nama Karoo, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 1999) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: An introduced cosmopolitan species known from both sexes, illustrated.

After Ono (2011)

Scytodes fusca female Photo Peter Webb

Scytodes gooldi Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Stompneus Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: VU National Criteria: B1ab(ii,iii)+2ab(ii,iii)

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Stompneus, St. Helena Bay. In South Africa only found only in the Western Cape where it is protected in the Table Mountain National Park and Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (EOO=6 313 km²; AOO=28 km²; 109-170 m a.s.l.). Known from seven locations, it is experiencing ongoing loss of habitat to crop cultivation and housing development therefore listed as Vulnerable under criterion B.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Malmesbury (-33.46, 18.74); St James (-34.11, 18.46); St. Helena Bay (-32.77, 18.03); Table Mountain National Park, Orange Kloof (-34.00, 18.24); Table Mountain National Park, Tokai S (-34.07, 18.4); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-33.5902, 18.2553).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface in the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There is ongoing loss of habitat to crop cultivation on the West Coast and to urban and coastal housing development throughout its range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known from both sexes, epigyne illustrated. Carapace with 3 black stripes above, the median stripe narrow but well developed, of equal width throughout behind the eyes and bordered on each side by a still narrower, straight, yellow line; the extremely broad, outer black bands with 2 pairs of yellow spots (one pair behind the lateral eyes and the other at the middle of the carapace). Sternum black with median yellow patch. Legs strongly banded with black and yellow. Abdomen with dark markings (Purcell 1904).

After Purcell (1904)

***Scytodes karrooica* Purcell, 1904**

COMMON NAME: Matjiesfontein Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from type locality Matjiesfontein. The species is known only from the type locality (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 912 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure as it was last sampled in 1903. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa: Western Cape.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface of the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats unknown but more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known only from a female, epigyne illustrated. Carapace with five black stripes, median stripe short. Abdomen pale with black transverse bands and spots. Femora of legs striped longitudinal (Purcell 1904) .

After Purcell (1904)

***Scytodes lanceolata* Purcell, 1904**

COMMON NAME: Hanover Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Hanover (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1358 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape*: Hanover (-30.94, 24.53).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface of the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES : Threats to the species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from a male, embolus illustrated. Carapace with 3 black stripes above, the median yellow stripe rather broad, the median black stripe very fine posteriorly and not reaching behind the middle of the carapace, the outer black stripes broad, each with a longitudinal series of 3 or 4 yellow spots or stripes; sides of carapace reticulated with black, showing several tiers of yellow spaces. Abdomen with transverse black bands and rows of spots. Femora of legs with black bar at apex, the anterior surface, at least in the anterior pairs, also sprinkled with black; tibia sparsely sprinkled with black, the apex with a black band (Purcell 1904).

After Purcell (1904)

***Scytodes lawrencei* Lessert, 1939**

COMMON NAME: Lawrence's Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Lessert (1939) from Democratic Republic of Congo. Known from several African countries. In South Africa it is under sampled and known only from the Eastern Cape and Limpopo (EOO<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 19-574 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range in Africa the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: East, Central Africa and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Mazeppa Bay (-32.47, 28.64). *Limpopo:* Ndengeza (-23.3165, 30.4114).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from both sexes, illustrated.

After Lessert (1939)

Scytodes leipoldti Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Clanwilliam Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Clanwilliam in the Western Cape. Also more recently sampled from the Northern Cape (EOO<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 78-199 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Namaqua National Park (-30.0109, 17.5797). *Western Cape:* Clanwilliam (-32.16, 18.89)

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface in the Fynbos and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES. Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from a female. Male collected but need to be described. Carapace with two narrow curved stripes on each side of the yellow median stripe (Purcell 1904).

Scytodes leipoldti undescribed male Namaqua NP Photo ASD

Scytodes lycosella Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Banded-leg Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Rietvlei Umvoti district (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1450 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure as last specimen was sampled in 1899. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Rietvlei (-29.18, 30.33); Umvoti (-29.25, 31.42).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spider collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Carapace with only 3 black stripes above; the median one abbreviated behind, reaching only to the middle of the carapace; the outer stripes very broad, nearly meeting posteriorly, each containing an oval yellow spot just before the middle of the carapace; the median yellow area just behind the median black stripe broad and spindle-shaped; sides of the carapace with black reticulation and several tiers of yellow areas. Legs very strongly banded, the femora with 3 strong black bands, the anterior pair also spotted with black near apex (Purcell 1904).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from a female, illustrated.

***Scytodes lyriformis* Purcell, 1904**

COMMON NAME: Karoo Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Hanover. The species is known only from the type locality (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1358 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure as it was last sampled in 1901. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Hanover (-30.94, 24.53).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spider collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface from the Nama Karoo Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from both sexes, not illustrated. Carapace with 5 black stripes above, but the median stripe short, continued only a little distance behind the median eyes; inner of the paired strips narrow, subparallel, somewhat remote from the outer stripes and connected before their middle with the latter by a transverse bridge, and often again at the outcurve anterior ends, the posterior ends converging and free; outer stripes not very broad; sides of the carapace with a row of black bordered yellow areas on each side and with black marks above and below these. Femora of legs striped longitudinally with rows of spots and black lines. This species scarcely differs from *S. subulata* and may be merely a colour variety (Purcell 1904).

Scytodes maritima Lawrence, 1938

COMMON NAME: Maritima Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1938) from Umhlali in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is recorded from three provinces including more than 10 protected areas (EOO=223 040 km²; AOO=120 km²; 27-2142m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ithala Nature Reserve Doornkraal Camp (-27.51, 31.20; Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Ndumo Game Reserve (26.87, 32.24); Ngome State Forest (-27.78, 31.45); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1); Tembe Elephant Park (-26.94, 32.47); Vryheid Nature Reserve (-27.75, 30.79); Umhlali nr. Balito (-29.47, 31.22); Malkerns Nyanza (-26.55, 31.18); iSimangaliso Wetland Park uMkhuze Game Reserve A (-27.6093, 32.2273); iSimangaliso Wetland Park uMkhuze Game Reserve B (-27.6268, 32.2366); iSimangaliso Wetland Park uMkhuze Game Reserve F (-27.6567, 32.2676); iSimangaliso Wetland Park uMkhuze Game Reserve H (-27.6181, 32.2294); iSimangaliso Wetland Park uMkhuze Game Reserve I (-27.6593, 32.2703); Midlands Good Hope plantation Boston (-29.3909, 29.5709); Oribi Gorge Nature Reserve (-30.71, 30.26). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Dendron (Farm Amsterdam) (-23.37, 29.32); Lhuvhondo Nature reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87); Lephahlale (-23.67, 27.7); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm The Downs (-24.14, 30.31); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Farm Malta (-24.1617, 30.2538); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Balloon Forest (-24.1994, 30.3388); Vhembe Biosphere Hanglip State Forest (-22.9988, 29.8859). **Mpumalanga:** Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96); Lowveld National Botanical Garden (-25.47, 31.00); Loskop Dam Resort (-25.42, 29.32); Mariepskop (-24.58, 30.87).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from tree and herb layer and from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. At Ndumo Game Reserve the species was also sampled from *Vachellia xanthophloea* bark (Haddad 2016). Sampled from the Forest, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013) as well as commercial pine plantations (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

After Lawrence (1938)

Scytodes maritima from Loskop Photo Peter Webb

Scytodes maritima from Legalameetse Photo Peter Webb

Scytodes maritima from Lephahlale Photo Peter Webb

***Scytodes maritima* (continued)**

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in several protected areas such as Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006), Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015), Legalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2016) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known from only females, illustrated.

Scytodes maritima from Lephahlale Photo Peter Webb

***Scytodes marshalli* Pocock, 1902**

COMMON NAME: Marshall's Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Pocock (1902) from Estcourt (EOO= <100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1152 m a.s.l.). The species is known only from the type locality. The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Estcourt (-29, 29.87).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface in the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES Threats to the species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised and known only from the female, epigynum illustrated.

After Pocock (1902)

Scytodes montana Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Table Mountain Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: Rare

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from top of Kalk Bay Mountains. The species is sampled from several localities in the Table Mountain National Park (EOO=215 km²; AOO=28 km²; 125-648 m a.s.l.). Only known from one sex this species has a restricted distribution and is listed as Rare.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Houhoek (-34.14, 19.04); Kalkbaai (-34.19, 18.42); Table Mountain National Park, Cecilia Spilhau (-34, 18.42); Table Mountain National Park, Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-33.98, 18.42); Table Mountain National Park, Newlands Forest(-33.97, 18.44); Table Mountain National Park, Orange Kloof (-34.00, 18.24); Table Mountain National Park, Tokai N (34.04, 18.4).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. The species was sampled with pitfall traps from the Fynbos Biome (Uys 2012).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from only female, epigyne illustrated. The spiders are pale yellow and the carapace decorated with five black stripes, the median stripe narrow covering the whole carapace; black stripes next to median one twice the width of median stripe and parallel with it extend from behind lateral eyes to highest point to suddenly curving outwards to unite with border stripes (Purcell 1904).

Scytodes quinqua Lawrence, 1927

COMMON NAME: Namibia Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1927) from Namibia. In South Africa known only from Limpopo (EOO=8 km²; AOO=8 km²; 894-1372 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo*: Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Little Leigh (Western Soutpansberg) (-22.95, 29.87).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface in the Savanna Biome (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species it is protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from juvenile, carapace illustrated. There is a short central stripe just behind the eyes which is continued in front of the eyes to the edge of the clypeus. Legs with coxae and trochanters without markings, except the first coxa which has an indistinct apical stripe legs seen from below; femora of I and II with an indistinct basal, a median, and an apical band, III and IV with irregular spots and blotches throughout (Lawrence (1927)

Scytodes quinqua male from Namibia Photo Anka Eichhoff

After Lawrence (1927)

Scytodes rubra Lawrence, 1937

COMMON NAME: Zululand Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1937) from Nkandla Forest in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from two provinces (EOO=35 965 km²; AOO=16 km²; 47-1102m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Addo Elephant National Park (-33.3434, 25.7391); *KwaZulu-Natal:* Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (-28.09, 32.1); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Nkandla Forest (-28.61, 31.09); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface from the Forest and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. It is protected in the Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006), Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015) and Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known from both sexes, illustrated. Female carapace in general, legs, sternum, coxae and mouth-parts reddish-brown; carapace with pattern markings as seen from above, the lighter parts orange, the darker parts a reddish-brown; chelicerae dark

Scytodes rubra from Addo NP Photo Linda Wiese

After Lawrence (1937)

Scytodes schultzei Purcell 1908

COMMON NAME: Steinkopf Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described Purcell (1908) from Steinkopf. Known only from the Northern Cape sampled from several localities (EOO=1 111km²; AOO=12 km²; 63-870 m a.s.l.). More sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic purposes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Northern Cape: Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73); Sendelingsdrif (-28.13, 16.90); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface in the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown. More sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species' range. Protected in the Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from only the female, epigyne illustrated.

10.
After Purcell (1908)

Scytodes silvatica Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Forest Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Knysna in the Western Cape. The species was sampled from two provinces (EOO=70 868 km²; AOO=20 km²; 1-1479m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Mkambathi Nature Reserve (31.32, 29.97); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Asante Sana Private Game Reserve (-32.282, 24.980); Tsitsikamma National Park (-33.58, 23.35). **Western Cape:** Knysna (-34.03, 23.03).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. The species was sampled from the Forest, Savanna and Ticket biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in the Mkambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2011), Asante Sana Private Game Reserve (Midgley 2012) and Tsitsikamma National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020).

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from both sexes, not illustrated. Colour a deep brown or purplish-black, mottled with yellow. Carapace with well-developed median stripe lying between a pair of broader yellow stripes, on each side of which is a very broad, curved, black band, the latter bearing a small yellow spot just before the middle of the carapace; sides of carapace broadly blackened inferiorly, with a row of 4 yellow spots on each side and a row of larger or smaller, more irregular yellow marks above these; posterior part of carapace with median yellow spot (Purcell 1904).

***Scytodes subulata* Purcell, 1904**

COMMON NAME: Stompneus Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DD

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Stompneus, St Helena Bay (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 109 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore listed as Data Deficient.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Western Cape:** Malmesbury (-33.46, 18.74); St. Helena Bay Stompneus (-32.77, 18.03).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spider collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface in the Fynbos Biome.

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Threats to the species are unknown.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known from both sexes, not illustrated. On the carapace the posterior half of each inner stripe is separated from the anterior half (which often ends free) just behind the transverse bridge which joins the outer and inner stripes while the femora of the legs are not spotted but provided with a very distinct basal, mesial, and distal black band. The markings closely resembling those of *S. leipoldti* (Purcell 1904).

Scytodes symmetrica Lawrence, 1938

COMMON NAME: Bulwer Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Lawrence (1938) from Bulwer. The species is known only from the type locality (EOO<100 km²; AOO=4 km²; 1534 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Bulwer (-29.79, 29.77).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spider collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface in the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Treats to the species are unknown. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from only female, illustrated.

After Lawrence (1938)

Scytodes testudo Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Cape Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Table Mountain National Park Lion's Hill. The species has been sampled from several localities in the province (EOO=31 249 km²; AOO=72 km²; 7-882 m a.s.l.). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Western Cape: Avontuur (-33.72, 23.16); Caledon (-34.24, 19.43); Table Mountain National Park Lion's Hill (-33.91, 18.42); Franschoek (-33.89, 19.1); Hottentots Holland Mts (-34.07, 18.56); Houhoek (-34.14, 19.04); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96); Kogsmans Kloof (-33.12, 20.87); Paarl (-33.71, 18.98); Rabiesberg (-33.36, 19.39); Riviersonderend (-34.15, 19.93); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Stellenbosch, Uitzicht (-33.93, 18.85); Stellenbosch Mooiplaas Edge (-33.9243, 18.7410); Stellenbosch Slent Farm Edge (-33.6212, 18.8169); Kuilsrivier (-33.93, 18.68); Swellendam (-34.02, 20.42); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47); Fish Hoek (-34.15, 18.42).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. Sampled from the Fynbos Biome. The species has also been found in vineyards around Stellenbosch (Theron et al. 2020).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known from both sexes, genitalia illustrated. Carapace with five stripes; median black stripe on carapace reaching the highest point; black stripes on both sides of the median stripe in turn at posterior end but united by thick transverse patch; outer stripe very thick ()-shaped. Abdomen banded and spotted (Purcell 1904).

Scytodes testudo female from Fish Hoek Photo Heather Hodgson

After Purcell (1904)

After Purcell (1904)

Scytodes thoracica (Latreille, 1802)

COMMON NAME: Yellow House Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A cosmopolitan species described in 1802. In South Africa recorded from three provinces (EOO=174 491 km²; AOO=32 km²; 68-1444 m a.s.l.). Due to the wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Europe, North Africa, Turkey, Asia to China, Korea, Japan, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Irene Smuts House (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Pongola, Farm Vergeval, district Ngqotshe (-27.35, 31.61); Vernon Crookes Nature Reserve (-30.16, 30.37); False Bay Park (-27.58, 32.22). **Limpopo:** Vhembe Biosphere Gonden Communal land (-22.9139, 30.0497); Vhembe Biosphere Barries Farm BAR08 (-22.4726, 29.4076); Vhembe Biosphere Barries Farm BAR06 (-22.4778, 29.4053); Vhembe Biosphere Barries Farm BAR01 (-22.4851, 29.4136); Vhembe Biosphere Blouberg Nature Reserve North (-22.9625, 29.1033).

LIFESTYLE: This is a cosmopolitan species frequently found in houses. Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface in the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: There are no significant threats to the species and it is protected in the Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019)

TAXONOMIC NOTES: An introduced cosmopolitan species. Known from both sexes.

After Brignoli (1969)

Scytodes thoracica Photo Peter Webb

***Scytodes triangulifera* Purcell, 1904**

COMMON NAME: Willowmore Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Prince Albert. Known from single localities in the Eastern and Western Cape sampled prior to 1904 (EOO<1000 km²; AOO=8 km²; 614-844 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore, listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5). *Western Cape:* Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spider collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface. Sampled from the Karoo and Succulent Karoo biomes.

CONSERVATION MEASURES : No threats known but more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised known from only the female, illustrated. Carapace with a single, very broad black band on each side of the median yellow stripe above Legs yellow, with dark markings as follows: femur I wholly dark, II dark with 2 yellow bands, III and IV yellow' with 2 or 3 dark bands, tibiae and metatarsi for the most part dark, tibiae III and IV

After Purcell (1938)

Scytodes trifoliata Lawrence, 1938

COMMON NAME: Port Shepstone Spitting Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1938) from Port Shepstone. Known from three provinces (EOO=44 738 km²; AOO=16 km²; 52-197 m a.s.l.). Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is therefore listed as Least Concern.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Port Shepstone (-30.74, 30.44). **Eastern Cape:** Cwebbe Nature Reserve The Haven (-32.28, 28.9); Kei River Mouth (-32.68, 28.37). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (Skukuza Camp) (-25, 31.97).

LIFESTYLE: Wandering spiders commonly collected from under stones and dark places on the soil surface from the Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, Savanna and Thicket biomes (Foord et al. 2011).

CONSERVATION MEASURES : There are no significant threats to the species. Protected in two protected areas: Cwebbe Nature Reserve and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020; Robertson et al. 2011)

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised, known only from the females.

After Lawrence (1938)

Pretoria Botaniese Tuin

Pretoria Botaniese Tuin

Opathe Game Reserve

Bloemfontein

Bloemfontein

Cederberg Wilderness Area

Scytodes multilineata?

Sani Pass

Tsipise J. Wilkinson

Swaziland Peter Webb

Pretoria Les Oates

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